

PERIODATES OF YTTRIUM, ERBIUM AND CERIUM.

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Yttrium, cerium and erbium resemble with the rest of the rare earths in forming the corresponding rare earth mesoperiodate YIO_5 usually with four molecules of water. Yttrium differs from the rest in forming an additional periodate, yttrium diorthoperiodate with eleven molecules of water, $Y_4I_2O_{13}, 11H_2O$, or $2Y_2O_3, I_2O_7, 11H_2O$.

Cleve found that yttrium acetate gives two periodates (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1874, 21, 196) $3Y_2O_3 \cdot 2I_2O_7, 6H_2O$ and $YIO_5, 4H_2O$. The latter was obtained by dissolving the precipitate formed by the interaction of paraperiodic acid and then recrystallising it out.

On repeating the above work, yttrium acetate was found to give only one periodate on its treatment with paraperiodic acid, namely the tetrahydrated yttrium mesoperiodate, $YIO_5, 4H_2O$.

A new yttrium periodate, *i.e.*, yttrium diorthoperiodate with eleven molecules of water, $Y_4I_2O_{13}, 11H_2O$ or $2Y_2O_3, I_2O_7, 11H_2O$ (described later) has also been obtained.

Tetrahydrated mesoperiodates were obtained in the case of erbium and cerium.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method of Preparation of the Periodates of Yttrium, Erbium and Cerium.

The preparation of the periodates of yttrium, erbium and cerium was carried out by the gradual addition of a dilute solution of paraperiodic acid to a cold solution of a soluble rare earth salt or by boiling a suspension of disodium paraperiodate with a solution of an excess of the soluble rare earth salt. In the latter case the mixture was boiled for half an hour to ensure complete reaction. The precipitate obtained in each case was filtered, washed and dried at 40° in an electric air oven.

The earth elements were estimated by igniting the periodates to oxides. Iodine and available oxygen were determined by the methods adopted by Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1085, 1087).

Periodates of Yttrium.

(a) A new salt, yttrium diorthoperiodate with eleven molecules of water, $Y_4I_2O_{13}, 11H_2O$ or $2Y_2O_3 \cdot I_2O_7, 11H_2O$ was formed by the interaction of disodium paraperiodate and yttrium acetate, in the form of a white precipitate; it formed a white amorphous powder in the dry state.

TABLE I.

Sample.	Y t t r i u m		I o d i n e		Available oxygen	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	35.44%	35.0%	25.20%	25.03%	10.67%	11.03%
2	35.01		25.13		10.42	
3	35.20		25.40		10.60	

Yttrium mesoperiodate with four molecules of water, $YIO_5, 4H_2O$ was obtained by the action of paraperiodic acid on yttrium acetate. This salt, which is in the form of a fine precipitate, dissolves in excess of paraperiodic acid and on crystallisation from this solution yields the same mesoperiodate (see A). We have been unable to prepare the salt $3Y_2O_3 \cdot 2I_2O_7, 6H_2O$ as claimed by Cleve (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE II.

Sample A is the recrystallised salt.

Sample.	Y t t r i u m		I o d i n e		Available oxygen	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	24.47%	24.12%	33.50%	34.54%	15.63%	15.23%
2	24.20		33.20		15.27	
3	24.22		33.54		15.30	
A	24.16		34.13		15.30	

Periodate of Erbium.

(b) *Tetrahydrated Erbium Mesoperiodate*, $\text{ErIO}_5 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was formed as a white gelatinous precipitate by boiling a solution of erbium nitrate with a suspension of disodium paraperiodate. It is a white powder in the dry state.

TABLE III.

Sample.	E r b i u m		I o d i n e		Available oxygen	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	36.10%	37.54%	28.60%	28.42%	12.60%	12.5%
2	36.30		29.31		12.90	
3	36.40		28.94		12.70	
4	36.30		29.00		12.80	

The slight discrepancies in the results of erbium and iodine are probably due to the presence of traces of other rare earths present in the erbium nitrate, which are very difficult to eliminate.

No precipitate was obtained by the addition of paraperiodic acid to cold or hot solution of erbium nitrate.

Periodate of Cerium.

(I) *Tetrahydrated Cerium Mesoperiodate*, $\text{CeIO}_5 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.—A yellow precipitate was obtained by the addition of a suspension of disodium paraperiodate to a boiling solution of cerium nitrate. It turned deep yellow on drying.

(II) The same salt was also obtained by the action of paraperiodic acid on cerium nitrate. In this case a white gelatinous precipitate, first formed, turned yellow on standing. We confirm this observation made by Cleve (*loc. cit.*).

The results given in Table IV show that the yttrium, erbium and cerium rare earths resemble each other in the formation of the same periodate, namely tetrahydrated rare earth mesoperiodate.

TABLE IV.

Samples A, prepared by method (I).
 Samples B, prepared by method (II).

Sample.	C e r i u m		I o d i n e		Available oxygen	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
A 1	33'70%	33'40%	29'82%	30'20%	11'60%	11'45%
2	33'61		30'27		11'61	
3	33'41		29'77		11'40	
B 1	33'10		29'86		11'53	
2	33'42		30'41		11'44	
3	33'51		30'12		11'44	

This corresponds with the results obtained in case of lanthanum and samarium (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1874, 21, 196 ; 1883, 39, 289). These form dihydrated lanthanum mesoperiodate $\text{LaIO}_5 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and tetrahydrated samarium mesoperiodate $\text{SmIO}_5 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. This confirms a close similarity between the different salts of the rare earths. Yttrium, however, differs from the rest in the formation of one more periodate, $\text{Y}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{13} \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $2\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{I}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

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